

ISic0079

Epitaph of Crispia Salvia

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

Metcalfe 2015.04.18

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

From the hypogeum of Crispia Salvia, on via Massimo D'Azeglio, Marsala ; three fragments remain in situ, the fourth now in the Baglio Anselmi museum. The hypogeum was excavated in 1996.

Coordinates

37.8044224,12.4372473

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo archeologico
regionale Lilibeo Marsala - Baglio Anselmi, inventory 3701

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Crispia □ Salvia
2. vixit aṅnos
3. plus miṅ,ṽs XLV
4. uxori dulcissimāe
5. Iulius Demetri
6. us maritus q̄uae
7. vixit cum suo
8. marito ann(os) XV
9. libenti animo

Apparatus

text after Bivona corrected against photographs

Translation (en)

Crispia Salvia lived for more or less 45 years. Iulius Demetrius her husband (set this up) for his most beloved wife, who lived with her husband for 15 years with a cheerful spirit.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491382

EDCS 3000420

Bibliography

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